

NANO-STRUCTURES OF PITCH-BASED CARBON FIBERS AND THE COMPATIBILITY WITH ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The degradation of pitch-based carbon fibers at the interface of aluminum and fibers which have wide range of Young's moduli and variety of structures has been studied. The tensile strengths of the composites before and after heating at 773-873K for 2h in Ar, have been examined. The X-ray structure parameters: $L_c(002)$ and d_{002} , and the nano-structures: radial-, random-, and onion-structure have been evaluated. The interfacial interaction of the fibers and aluminum has been discussed with the results of TEM and EDX. The tensile strength changes drastically with nano-structural difference. The onion structured fibers where the basal planes of graphitic sheets are oriented in the direction of parallel to the surface, show less reactivity with aluminum than the other structured fibers. It follows from this that structurally controlled pitch-based carbon fibers are effective to enhance the properties of the carbon fiber reinforced aluminum.

KEYWORDS: pitch-based carbon fibers, $L_c(002)$, d_{002} , random-, radial-, onion- structure, compatibility, aluminum .

INTRODUCTION

Recently pitch-based carbon fibers of various types of structure and wide variety of Young's moduli (E), derived from a coal or a petroleum pitch, have been developed. Although a large number of researches have been carried out into carbon fiber/aluminum composite system [1-9], little is known about the compatibility of those various pitch-based carbon fibers with aluminum.

It has been known that more graphitized pitch-based carbon fibers are less reactive with aluminum than PAN based carbon fibers [4]. The fact suggests that pitch-based carbon fibers have advantage in the reinforcement for aluminum matrix composites. Kohara and Muto reported that the different structure of aluminum carbide crystal caused different kinds of the fracture at the interface of PAN based-carbon fibers and aluminum [7].

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the compatibility with pitch-based carbon fibers and aluminum for the development of aluminum matrix composites. The changes in tensile strength of pitch-based carbon fibers/aluminum before and after heat treatment have been investigated.

The X-ray structure parameters and the nano-structures of the pitch-based carbon fibers have been examined. The interface interaction of the fibers and aluminum have been discussed with TEM and EDX analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Pitch-based Carbon Fibers/Aluminum Composites

MOCVD from tri-isobutyl aluminum was applied for preparations of pitch-based carbon fibers/aluminum composites. Aluminum of 1 μ m thick was formed on carbon fibers uniformly without degradation by CVD process at 533K in deposition temperature, 3990Pa in Ar, whose throwing power for the multifilament was excellent. The pitch-based carbon fibers used and PAN-based carbon fibers for comparison are listed in Table 1. The fibers represented by NS - were supplied from Nippon steel Co., XN-, JIS- were from Nippon Petrochemicals Co., Ltd., P- was from The Union Carbide Co. currently renamed as Amoco Performance Products Co., and T300 and M40 were from Torey Co.

The pitch-based carbon fibers/ aluminum composites were heated at 773- 873K for 7.2ks in Ar of 96 kPa. Some composites after the heat treatment were immersed into a 5 mass% HF aqueous solution at room temperatures in a few minutes until dissolving out aluminum.

Table 1: Properties of the carbon fibers

fiber	tensile strength	E	$L_c(002)$	d_{002}	nano-structure	remark
NS-20	2068MPa	189GPa	2.56 nm	0.3456 nm	random	1
XN-30	3230MPa	294GPa	6.97 nm	0.3458 nm	radial	2
NS-30	2538MPa	309GPa	-	-	random	1
P-55	2069MPa	379GPa	14.0 nm	0.3439 nm	radial	2
NS-40	2597MPa	404GPa	8.85 nm	0.3430 nm	random	2
XN-50	3230MPa	490GPa	15.8 nm	0.3428 nm	radial	1
JIS-50	3880MPa	505GPa	14.1 nm	0.3445 nm	onion	2
XN-60	3230MPa	588GPa	-	-	radial	2
NS-60	2734MPa	597GPa	20.3 nm	0.3442 nm	random	1
XN-70	3293MPa	666GPa	19.9 nm	0.3412 nm	radial	2
JIS-70	3961MPa	704GPa	16.4 nm	0.3433 nm	onion	2
T300	3100MPa	250GPa	1.6 nm	0.3613 nm	particle	PAN
M40	4410MPa	392GPa	3.0 nm	0.3560 nm	particle	PAN

1:coal-pitch, 2:petroleum-pitch

Tensile Strength of the Pitch-based Carbon Fibers/Aluminum

The ultimate tensile strengths of the composites and fibers were quantified by a tensile machine (Minebea TCM-50). The tensile speed was 8m/s. More than 20 specimens in every series were applied for testing. All the data were evaluated with the Weibull analysis to compare the mean value, the variation coefficient and the Weibull parameter for each series.

Analysis by SEM, XRD, TEM and EDX The interlayer spacing between graphitic planes: d_{002} of the pitch-based carbon fibers and the thickness of graphitic crystallite: $L_c(002)$, were determined from the (002) profile obtained. The peak position and the width at half maximum intensity of the corrected profiles supplied the values of d_{002} and $L_c(002)$.

To confirm and quantify the aluminum carbide formation of heat treated P-55/aluminum composite at 773-873K for 7.2ks, gas chromatogram (Simadu GC 9A) and 40kV XRD (Rigaku GFX-RAD3C) were used.

The interfaces of pitch-based carbon fibers/ aluminum after the heat treatment were analyzed with TEM and EDX. The TEM studies were carried out on 300kV TEM instrument (Hitachi H-9000HR). The EDX studies were carried out on FESTEM instrument (VG HB501) and 100kV XMA instrument (KEVEX DELTA) whose probe was 1nm ϕ .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Strength of the Pitch-based Carbon Fibers/Aluminum Composites

The relative tensile strength of the pitch-based carbon fibers/aluminum composite based on Weibull analysis are shown in Fig. 1. Here, the relative strength means the value divided the second tensile strength after some treatments by the original tensile strength of pitch-based carbon fibers. With the increase of the Young's modulus of the fibers (E), the relative tensile strength divided the strength of the aluminum coated fibers by the tensile strength of the no-coated fibers before heat treatment, decreases. The relative strengths of coal pitch-based carbon fibers/aluminum are slightly higher than 1. On the other hand, the relative strength of petroleum pitch-based carbon fiber/aluminum with heat treatment is slightly less than 1, in spite of the same fabrication condition and the same heat treatment are applied. The pitch-based carbon fiber recovers its original strength, if there is no degradation in the fibers. In other words, the decrease of the strength of fibers removed from aluminum is interpreted as fiber degradation itself. The tensile strength of pitch-based carbon fibers removed from aluminum without heat treatment tend to recover its original strength. The relative strength removed from aluminum after heat treatment, however, decreased gradually as a function of the Young's modulus.

symbols	radial	random	onion	PAN	Al removal
before heating	△	○	□	☆	
after heating	▲	●	■	★	X □ ☆

Figure 1. Changes in the relative tensile strengths of carbon fibers/aluminum composites and aluminum removal fibers

Fiber Strength after Removal of Aluminum

Here, as shown in Fig. 1, the relative tensile strengths of the fibers are examined after the aluminum is dissolved in a 5 mass% aqueous solution of HF. Generally after the aluminum is removed the fiber should exhibit its original properties, unless fiber degradation has occurred due to the aluminum coating. Heat treatment at 773-873K should promote stress relaxation even if any change in relative fracture strength has occurred due to internal stress. Examination of Fig. 1 from this angle leads to the judgment that the strength degradation in a fiber with a Young's modulus of 200-300 GPa is due to a decrease in the cross-sectional area of the fiber accounted for by the reaction products.

Fibers with a Young's modulus of more than 500 GPa (except those with an onion structure) tended to degrade, indicating a relative fracture strength of 1 or less for the fibers after aluminum removed. However, the carbide concentration (as calculated from the thickness of the black band by TEM observation) tended to decrease for fibers with a higher Young's modulus. In the XN-70/Al composite, the black-band part became discontinuous, indicating that the concentration was even lower.

There are two conceivable mechanisms for the degradation in strength of aluminum reinforced with carbon fibers.

- (1) Fiber's section reduction mechanism [1]
- (2) Notching stress concentration mechanism [2]

Owing to the variety of fibers and their structures, it can be easily be supposed that these mechanisms have varying degrees of involvement. Kohara and Muto reported that the pattern of carbide development differed depending on the type of PAN-based carbon fiber. They showed that in the case of PAN-based carbon fiber with high modulus, degradation of strength occurs due to the notch effect, since carbide also develops on the inside of the fiber [7].

The similarity between the strength degradation of pitch-based carbon fiber and that of PAN-based carbon fiber gives rise to the possibility that the same type of carbide development will occur also in pitch-based carbon fibers.

X-ray Structural Parameters of the Pitch-based Carbon Fibers and SEM Images

Lc(002) and d_{002} of the carbon fibers determined are shown in Table 1. The images of a scanning electron microscopy of the fractured surface of the pitch based carbon fibers show that the NX- fibers and P-55 fiber have a radial structure, and the NS- fibers have a random structure. JIS- fibers have an onion structure. The different structure of carbon fibers will exert influence on the physical and chemical interaction with aluminum. In other words, it will induce different residual stresses and different reactivity.

Analysis for the Interface Interaction by TEM and EDX

To compare various pitch-based carbon fibers in terms of interface interaction such as carbide formation, TEM observation was performed on the interfaces of fiber-aluminum composites. The fibers tested were NS-20, P-55, NS-60, XN-70, and JIS-70 heat-treated at 773K for 7.2ks.

Fig. 2 nano-structures of pitch-based carbon fibers left: radial structure, middle: onion structure, right: random structure

The results show that a contrasting black-band layer of reaction products formed in the neighborhood of the interface, except in the JIS-70/Al composite of an onion structure. In the NS-20/Al composite, a layer approximately 10 nm thick formed along the outer circumference of the fiber, as shown in Fig. 4. Assuming that there is a uniform layer of reaction products approximately 10nm thick, 5ppm of reaction products will form per unit volume of coated aluminum. However, the said presumed amount of reaction products is extremely low in comparison with the 200ppm of formed carbide obtained by gas chromatography [10].

The point analysis by EDX showed that the black-band layer contained 21 mass% oxygen, and 3 mass% carbon. In contrast, the inner part of the fiber consisted of 100 mass% carbon and the non-black-band layer contained 98 mass% aluminum or more. With line analysis,

gentle concentration gradients were obtained for both carbon and aluminum, while the profile for oxygen had a peak on the interface, suggesting that a concentration of oxygen exists at the interface.

As shown in Fig. 4, similar results were obtained with the P-55/Al composite. The black band had a thickness of approximately 10nm, which was nearly equal to that of the NS20/Al composite.

Figure 3. TEM and EDX of NS-20/Al(773K,2h), Figure 4. TEM of P-55/Al(773K,2h)

Furthermore, as seen in the upper and lower right parts of Fig. 4, the black-band part shows a number of protuberances as if indicating a process of tissue proliferation; carbon appears to have diffused into the aluminum. Fig. 6 shows a TEM image of the NS-60/Al composite. Here, the average thickness of the black-band layer decreased to approximately 5nm. Since a clear lattice pattern was observed in some areas, the spacing of lattice planes was found by magnifying the lattice. On the assumption that a lattice that would provide aluminum with the maximum strength would be caused by the Al (111) plane, since $d=2.33 \text{ \AA}$ the spacing of lattice planes in the part derived from the reaction products would be about 4 \AA . This is very close to the $d=4.22 \text{ \AA}$ at $I/O=100$ for the (111) plane of oxycarbide ($\text{Al}_4\text{O}_4\text{C}$). When this is taken into consideration along with the presence of a great deal of oxygen and little

carbon, the possibility arises that oxycarbide is present as a reaction product. When the result of XRD shown in Fig. 6 was assigned with JCPDS in the light of this possibility, the minute peaks could be identified more precisely and were found to be identical with the JCPDS standard peaks for Al_2OC , and Al_4O_4C , thus confirming their presence.

Figure 5. TEM and EDX of NS-60/Al (773K, 2h), Figure 6. XRD of P-55/Al (773K, 2h)

Furthermore, a notch never before observed in any other fiber was discovered on the circumferential surface of the fiber of the NS-60/Al composite. The observational results for this are shown in Fig. 5(b).

In addition, the observational results for the XN-70/Al composite are shown in Fig. 7. Unlike the previous observation, there are some parts where aluminum in particle form seems to have obtruded into the fiber surface. These may be parts where the fiber surface has high reactivity. A black-band was detected here as well, with analytical results similar to those previously obtained. However, the oxygen and carbon contents were relatively high, 36 mass% and 19 mass%, respectively. On the other hand, in the SEM picture shown in Fig. 8, no black band was observed in the JIS-70/Al complex with an onion structure. However, an oxygen concentration remarkably lower than in previous composites and a comparatively steep gradient of aluminum or carbon concentration were found in the line profiles by EDX. In previously mentioned series, oxygen was clearly detected in the black-band part, but this oxygen had been derived from oxygen and water absorbed on the fiber surface. Here, the

amount absorbed should depend on the nano-structure of the fiber. Hennig [11], who studied the oxidative reaction of single crystal graphite below 1073 K, reported that molecular oxygen reacted preferentially with carbon on the edge plane of graphite crystal, while it reacting little with carbon on the basal plane. Reasoning based on the report, it is anticipated that the oxygen absorption properties will vary with the nano-structure of the fiber. That is, it is presumed that water will be most easily absorbed on the surface of a fiber of radial structure, and least easily on the surface of an onion structure. Murayama and Ohuchi have reported that oxygen absorbed on the surface accelerated the formation of carbide [12]. Considering all these factors, it can safely be said that a fiber which allows more oxide and/or absorbed oxygen to exist on its surface will form carbide more easily. Water and oxygen will not easily absorb into an onion structure, since the surface consists of basal planes. Hence there will be only a small amount of oxide on the surface. These expectations accord with the fact that a distinct black band did not appear in the TEM image.

Reactivity of Pitch-based Carbon Fiber with Aluminum

The reactivity of pitch-based carbon fiber with aluminum may be considered as follows. As shown in Fig. 9, fiber with a low Young's modulus has high reactivity with aluminum and reaction proceeds uniformly over the entire fiber surface. In contrast, fiber with a high Young's modulus has low reactivity due to its highly developed graphite crystalline. Therefore, it is expected that strength will decrease greatly in the latter fiber due to

the notch effect, if any locally weak parts, e.g., parts that are highly reactive due to minute defects, initiate reactions.

It is clear that in an onion structure the carbide layer is very thin and that the fiber degradation is comparatively minor. This means that the fiber of an onion structure itself has some sort of diffusion barrier layer, thereby suggesting the possibility that it may be usable without any special coating.

On the other hand, the oxidation velocity of carbon fiber reached a minimum at the diameter of the graphite crystals around $d_{002} = 0.342\text{nm}$ [13]. The reason for this has been discussed as follows. The oxidation tends to proceed during the underdeveloped stage of the graphite crystalline, while defects develop as the graphite crystalline develops, thereby allowing oxygen to diffuse. These defects promote oxidation until the oxidation velocity reaches a minimum at a certain point. It is not clear whether the same would be applicable to reactivity between aluminum and graphite, but as described earlier, it is clear that oxygen has a significant effect at least on the formation of carbide, so from this point of view it is possible that a similar process may occur. When Fig. 1 is reviewed in terms of the degradation of the carbon fiber after the aluminum is removed, carbon fiber with a Young's modulus of approximately 400GPa may be interpreted as being comparatively good compatibility with aluminum. However, another view is that there will be problems associated with its properties and reactivity from the aspect of the size of the graphite crystalline [14].

Fig. 9. The morphology of aluminum carbide formation and the relationship with the Young's moduli.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results and considerations described above, as a design guideline for compound materials with enhanced performance it is recommended that when aluminum is reinforced with some kind of pitch-based carbon fiber, pitch-based carbon fiber with an onion structure where the basal planes are oriented in the direction of parallel to the fiber circumferential surface should be used as filament reinforcements. On the other hand, when any kind of pitch-based carbon fiber with a high modulus of elasticity is used, special precautions should be taken against possible fiber degradation.

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